

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B252
Date: 13 December 2006
Take Off 11:27:36Z
Landing: 16:53:52Z
Flight Time 5h26m16

Campaign: WINTEX – Ice Nucleation in Lee Wave Clouds

Operating Area: NW Wales

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Richard Cotton	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist 2	Steven Abel	Met Office
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Flight Track:

B252 Track 13-DEC-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b252
 Date: 13 Dec 2006
 Project: WINTEX Ice Nucleations
 Location: NW Wales

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
101541		Start-Up	0.16 kft	127	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
105855		INU	0.16 kft	127	To Navigate Mode
112736		T/O	1.7 kft	307	Cranfield
114008		Heimann	10.0 kft	255	Cal 12 to 7 degC
114320		Videos	10.0 kft	256	Start FFC & RFC
120320		Heimann	20.0 kft	299	Cal 5 to -2degC
122429	123248	Profile 1	30.0 - 21.0 kft	173	Interrupt
123450	124116	Profile 1	21.0 - 15.0 kft	351	
124517	125019	Run 1	20.0 kft	266	Clear Air
125222	130143	Run 2	20.0 kft	083	Towards Snowdon
130610	132207	Run 3	20.0 kft	256	Recip 15nm south
131508		Videos	20.0 kft	264	Change Tapes
132144		Heimann	20.0 kft	264	Cal
132613	133547	Run 4	23.0 kft	083	Thru cloud
133824	134125	Run 5.1	24.5 kft	272	Thru cloud
134420	134544	Run 5.2	24.5 kft	016	Contrailing, just!
134908	135215	Run 6	25.0 kft	282	
135614	135852	Run 7	25.5 kft	096	Above cloud
140225	140558	Run 8	25.1 - 25.0 kft	304	Turb P Pitot iced up
141016	141312	Run 9	24.5 kft	121	In cloud
141548	141920	Run 10	24.0 kft	292	Contrailing
142256	142541	Run 11.1	23.5 - 23.6 kft	100	
142912	143214	Run 11.2	23.6 - 23.5 kft	284	
143647	143850	Run 12	23.1 kft	091	
144135	144619	Run 13	22.5 kft	288	Thru cloud
144710		Video	22.0 kft	228	Change Tapes
145429	145613	Run 14	22.0 kft	114	Contrailing
145822	150211	Run 15	23.6 - 23.5 kft	322	In Cloud Top
150711	150957	Run 16	23.1 kft	108	
151136		Event	22.3 kft	275	Descend to Clear Turb Probe
152601	153126	Profile 2	5.0 - 10.0 kft	195	
153249	154329	Profile 2	10.0 - 22.0 kft	336	Turb P cleared @1532
154529	155000	Profile 2	22.0 - 27.0 kft	181	
155733	155929	Run 17	23.0 - 23.1 kft	088	Cloud dissipated
160313	160901	Run 18	25.0 kft	288	Thru cloud?
161326	161726	Run 19.1	27.0 kft	090	In Cirrus
161849	162213	Run 19.2	27.0 kft	189	
162124		Videos	27.0 kft	167	End of tapes
165352		Land	0.23 kft	211	Cranfield
165831		Shutdown	0.22 kft	310	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B252 Track 13-DEC-06

Sortie Brief: WINTEX: Ice Nucleation in Lee-Wave Clouds

Flight Number: B252

Date: 13/12/2006

Sortie Aims: To observe the nucleation and early growth stages of ice particles in lee-wave clouds and to examine the performance of SID-2 in detecting first ice formation.

Sortie Location: Within a lee-wave cloud system over a mountain region of the UK (N.Wales, N.Pennines, Highlands).

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs along the mean wind direction through a lee-wave cloud system. The runs will commence in clear air upwind of the cloud and terminate in clear air downwind or after a minimum distance of 20km. Profile descents or dropsonde launches may be located upwind of the mountain region of interest. The aircraft may loiter or fly a short acrosswind leg upwind of the target cloud, for the purpose of sampling aerosol entering the cloud.

Sortie Detail:

- a) T+0 Take off and climb for transit to pre-defined operating area. The initial aiming point, **A**, will be a point over the sea upwind of the mountain region. Transit altitude as convenient but plan to arrive at **A** at FL300 (50 min).
- b) T+50 Profile descent from FL300 to FL150 (or -15 degC level, whichever is the lower) 1000ft/min (15 min)
- c) T+65 Perform a series of straight and level runs parallel to the mean wind direction so as to penetrate the wave cloud. Each leg will typically be a maximum of 5 min duration from clear air upwind to clear air downwind of the target cloud. Each wave cloud will be penetrated a minimum of 6 times. These penetrations may either be at the same or differing altitudes (45 mins).
- d) Cloud penetrations will normally be within the temperature range of about -15 to -35 degC. However, if there is a clear formation of orographic cirrus at -40 degC or below, cloud penetrations may also be flown at these levels.
- e) T+110 Transit to point **A** and profile descent FL300 to FL150 (25 min).
- f) T+135 Repeat c) and d) (70 min)
- g) T+205 If time permits, repeat c) and d) (70 min)
- h) T+275 Return transit (50 min)
- i) T+325 Land.

Philip R.A. Brown

Sortie Title: Ice nucleation in Lee-Wave clouds

Scientific Aims:

The purpose of this sortie is to achieve detailed sampling of the regions of a cloud in which nucleation of ice particles is occurring. Lee-wave clouds formed by the flow of stably-stratified air over a mountain are chosen for this purpose, since the predictability of the flow means that it is relatively simple to determine the trajectories followed by the air parcels that are sampled. These air trajectories typically oscillate in the vertical with an amplitude typically of a few hundred metres and a horizontal wavelength of 10-20km.

The aim is to fly a number of legs parallel to the mean wind direction through the observed cloud. The vertical separation between these legs will be typically 1-2000ft with a view to flying around 6-8 different vertical levels in the cloud. Measurements made along each run can then be compared with predictions from an explicit numerical model of the droplet condensation and ice nucleation processes. The horizontal legs start or terminate in clear upwind of the cloud, so as to enable sampling of the aerosol particles that enter the cloud. Flight leg altitudes are chosen to be in the temperature range of approximately -15 to -35 degC.

Weather conditions

A stably-stratified flow over a mountain region of the British Isles – likely candidates are the Scottish Highlands, N.Pennines or N.Wales. A particularly favourable situation is when the warm sector of an open-wave depression is situated over the topography. The warm conveyor belt of such a system provides moist air at mid-levels in the troposphere so as to form deep wave cloud systems in the required temperature regime. Infra-red satellite imagery may also be used to identify typical stationary edges of cirrus at colder temperatures aligned roughly perpendicular to the mean wind direction. Sampling in the leading edge of such cirrus bands is also desirable.

Key measurements

Johnson-Williams LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. If possible, these should be zeroed whilst in clear air approaching the cloud on a downwind leg.

Cloud physics – normal operations. Ensure that time offsets between SEADAS, FFSSP and SID-1/2 PCs are noted.

B252 debrief

Lee-wave cloud ice nucleation flight

General overview

A single isolated wave cloud was sampled but this consisted predominantly of super-cooled liquid water even though the temperature was around -30C. The turbulence probe iced up during the measurement and was not cleared until later. The first three runs were carried out in clear air and should provide a good test of the wind prediction model. The operating area over Snowdonia is very difficult.

Weather

Operating in a warm sector with the low centre over Scotland, and strong westerly winds. There was extensive cloud above and below with a generally clear layer at mid-levels. In the clear layer, there was some isolated clouds.

Operating area

Because of ATC restrictions, the operating area was very difficult. Only one cloud in the wave-train was able to be sampled because of trans-Atlantic airways. If the winds prediction is correct, and the moisture is sufficient, and (this was the problem for this flight) there are suitable IN, then a good measure of a single isolated wave cloud is possible however.

Profile P1 (FL300 to FL150) upwind of Snowdonia, was mostly in clear air with moist layers between FL265 and FL250 (around -35C) and between FL237 and FL219 (around -28C).

Runs R1 (inbound), R2 (outbound) and R3 (inbound) were all in clear air and should provide a good test of the winds prediction model. At this point the turbulence probe was operating normally.

An isolated cloud was observed and 'aimed' at for R4 (approx. inbound) at FL230 (-27C). The run was started in-cloud which was sampled near the base.

During R5.1 (outbound) at FL245, aircraft icing was observed. Wave-cloud position was 53 08.05N, 3 37.20W

R 5.2 repositioned because of ATC.

R6 (outbound) at FL250 extended further west to get a better view of the cloud to aim at the cloud centre to see if the cloud is stationary (orographic) (-28C).

R7 (inbound) at FL255, definite 'ice-like' wave cloud observed downwind (the next wave), but this was in the airway.

r8 (outbound) at FL250. The turbulence probe ice up. Because this flight is principally a SID2 test flight, and this is the only cloud that can be sampled, further runs were made before attempting to de-ice the turbulence probe, before the cloud dissipated.

r9 (inbound) at FL245.

r10 (outbound) at FL240

r11.1 (inbound) at FL235.

r11.2 (outbound) at FL235 after ATC holds altitude.

r12 (inbound) at FL230. Observe our faint contrails from last run.

r13 (outbound) at FL225. 144545 out of sharp cloud edge.

r14 (inbound) at FL220. Cloud much more widespread at this level. The lower cloud seems to have been extending during the sortie.

r15 (outbound) at FL235 (-28C). Out of cloud 150110. Cloud probes see some ice.

r16 (inbound) at FL235. Near cloud top now. So height range and extent of cloud is varying.

Rapid descent to try and de-ice turbulence probe before returning to this cloud. But probe does not de-ice quickly because the temperature is around 0C at lowest altitude.

Start profile P2 from FL050 to FL270. Turbulence probe clears during profile at 1532. On returning to wave cloud location it was difficult to observe because it was getting dark.

Sample cirrus above to SID2 ice particles in R19.1 and R19.2 at FL270.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.252**
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 Date **13 Dec 06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
112736					Take-off completed
					During climb out, cloud extensive upper and lower but transit in clear air.
114555		FL100			T: -3°C Td: -4.5°C 7/8 Ci 7/8 C
					Mid-level ^{some} isolated clouds
120030		FL200		52° 12.0W 2° 30.0W	T: -20°C Td: -27°C Some mid-level patchy cloud. wind 23 m/s ¹ at 267°
121040		FL200			In thin cloud, near top, turbulent T: -20°C
121450		FL300			In cloud. SID 2/1 particles
122429	Plst	FL300			Start in cloud.
122540					Near base T: -27°C, FL 265 moist layer.
122955		FL237			T: -30°C enter ^{-FL250} cloud. Turb.
123200		FL219			Near base T: -25°C into clear air
124111	Pl end	FL150			
					Will do first run at FL200 inbound Towards Sweden
					In clear air to see if can find isolated cloud.
		Too much cloud.			
124517	R/1st	FL200			Clear air Inbound from Sweden

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.152**.....

 Date **13/12/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125017	R1 _{end}				Reposition 15m south to find clearance of mid level cloud.
125222	R2 _{st.}	FL200			Reciprocal outbound
	R2 _{end}				In clear air 8/8 above and below.
130610	R3 _{st.}	FL200			In bound clear air
132207	R3 _{end}				
					will return higher and aim at cloud. Start run includ
132613	R4 _{st}	FL230			T: -27°C very thin, near base.
133547	R4 _{end}				
133827	R5-1 _{st}	FL245			outbound into snowdon wave-cloud aircraft icing.
					Just trying to find location of wave cloud Lat/long.
134125	R5-1 _{end}				53° 08.05 N 3° 37.20 W
134420	R5-2 _{st}	FL245			Just repositioning.
	R5-2 _{end}				ATC difficult.
134901	R6 _{st}	FL250			Start out of cloud
					extend run further west
					will return to see if cloud is in same position.
					T: -28°C,
135215	R6 _{end}				above cloud.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

unclear
↓

exterior
1000 ft
○
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
135614	R7 _{ft}	FL255			Wave down in distance, but
135852	R7 _{end}				out of area.
140340		Turb/ Pilot		iced up.	
140225	R8 _{ft}	FL250			TW increased LWC
140558	R8 _{end}				
141016	R9 _{ft}	FL245			in front down
141112	R9 _{end}				
141545	R10 _{ft}	FL240			outbound. LWC observed
141920	R10 _{end}				
142258	R11 _{ft}	FL235			
142541	R11 _{end}				are holds alt. for return
142912	R12 _{ft}	FL235			
143217	R12 _{end}				
					more down below, so keep
143647	R12 _{ft}	FL230			descending. observe aircraft-trails but miss them...
143850	R12 _{end}				Keep measuring this cloud. Shannon - boundary of Sweden,
144135	R13 _{ft}	FL225			entering lower cloud.
144617	R13 _{end}				144545 out of sharp edge.
145427	R14 _{ft}	FL220			In cloud at start of run. (cloud widespread at this level.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
145822	R15 _{ft}	FL235			T: -28C Td: -27.5 wind 12/270
150211	R15 _{ce}				out of cloud 150110
					Some ice noted on cloud probes
					Solid cloud above and below
					mostly cloud in mid-level.
					x-wave cloud in distance.
					airway cannot enter.
					Must be second peak in wave-train
					more isolated than ours.
150711	R16 _{ce}	FL275			near cloud for
150757	R16 _{ce}				
					Rapid descent to then
					level probe. T=0 at FL076
152601	P2 _{ft}	FL005			Ascent
155000	P2 _{ce}	FL270			
					Return to 'our' cloud.
155771	R17 _{ft}	FL210			dark, not really obvious.
155721	R17 _{ce}				
160710	R18 _{ft}	FL250			Ascent into cloud above.
160901					
161226	R19 _{ft}	FL270			In cirrus
					level at base near start

Mission Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
112844	T10				Cranfield
					2D-C noisy. Switched off
					CP will restart before cloud work.
120650					S10-2 histogram looks like some ice particles. T=-20
122229		FL300			Contrailing (missed start)
122240					Contrail stop T-46.5 Td-44
122429	PI ↓ START	FL300	173	53.1N 4.6W	Profile descent to FL150 Upwind of mountains. Dry slot ~ 320 - 350 mbar Moist below. In cloud ~ 390 mbar Out cloud ~ 460 mbar T=-22.5
123248	PI ↓	FL210			Profile interrupted
123450	PI ↓	FL210		52.3N 4.3W	Profile restarted Very dry below 450 mbar.
124116	PI END	FL150			Profile end.
124517	R1-1	FL200	266	52.9N 4.5W	T=-22.3 Td=-43 START RUN
125019	R1-1	FL200		52.9N 4.5W	END RUN
125222	R1-2	FL200	083	53.0N 3.5W	START RUN heading toward Snowdon. T=-22 Td=-46
125800					Downdraft ~ 2ms ⁻¹ ?
125950					w ↑ ~ 5ms ⁻¹ from peak downdraft (-peak to trough). No cloud
130143	R1-2	FL200	087	53.0N 3.5W	END. Transit South ~ 15 miles
130610	R1-3	FL200	256	58.2N 3.5W	Smaller variations in w

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13.22.07	R1.3	FL200			RUN END
13.25.00		FL230			In cloud briefly - patchy cloud
132630	R4.1	FL230	083	52.9N 5.1W	LWC = 0.05 gm ⁻³ RUN START Heading back towards Snowden area.
133600					Some evidence of waves though to peak ~ 3ms ⁻¹
133547	R4.1	FL230	086	53.1N 3.5W	RUN END. Heading N to try and find wave clouds
133824	R5.1	FL245	272	53.1N 3.4W	RUN START T = -29.7 Td = -30.7 Cloud just below us at 13.39.15 Enter cloud ~ 13.39.40 LWC ~ 0.05 gm ⁻³ .
134125	R5.1	FL245	263		END.
134420	R5.2	FL245			START SID-2 possibly
134546	R5.2	FL245			END some small ice particles Continuing to aim for same cloud.
134908	R6.1	FL250		53.1N 3.5W	START T = -32
135215	R6.1	FL250			END
135614	R7.1	FL255		53.1N 4W	START. Aim for same cloud 13.59.20 Just above cloud
135852	R7.1	FL250		53.1N 4W	END T = -32
140225	R8	FL250			PITOT STATIC SIGNAL LOOKS LIKE ICED UP SID2 showing small signal in all channels. at ~140400

DOWNWARD CAMERA → CONTRAST v. POOR & MOTION AREA 1 CALAR

Mission Scientist's Log

MISSION SCI 2
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
140558	R8	FL250			END
141016	R9	FL245		53.2N 3.9W	START T _r = -29
141312	R9				END SID 2 again showing small signal in all detectors
141548	R10	FL240		53.1N 3.4W	START
141746					SID-2 detectors all showing small signal - little evidence of particles. LWC ~ 0.1 gm ⁻³
141920	R10	FL240			END
142256	R11	FL235		53.2N 3.9W	START
142405					SID 2 as previous runs LWC ~ 0.05 gm ⁻³
142541	R11	FL235		53.2N 3.5W	END. Turbulence probe still iced up
142912	R11.2	FL235		53.1N 3.5W	START
143017					SID 2 as in previous runs LWC ~ 0.05 gm ⁻³
143146					" " " " LWC ~ 0.05 gm ⁻³
143214	R11.2	FL235			END
143647	R12	FL230			START
143720					SID 2 as previous LWC ~ 0.04 gm ⁻³
143850	R12	FL230			END
144135	R13	FL225		53.1N 3.4W	START T _r = -26
144340					SID 2 as before. Longer bracket through cloud this time LWC ~ 0.04
144619	R13	FL225		53.2N 3.8W	END
145429	R14	FL220		53.2N 3.8W	START T _r = -26 T _d = -21
145525					SID 2 as in previous runs LWC ~ 0.04

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
145613	R14	FL220			END
145822	R15	FL235			START
					SIDZ again showing small response in all detectors. LWC = 0.18 gm^{-3}
150211	R15	FL235			END
150711	R16	FL230	108	53-IN 3.9W	START T = -25 Td = -30
150830					In cloud SIDZ as in previous run LWC = 0.13 gm^{-3}
150957	R16	FL230			END
151136					Descending to clear turbulence probe. Heading west
152552		FL50			T = +3.5° Turbulence centre part not clearing. Give up.
152601	P2↑	FL50	195	52.6N 4.3W	START part
152817					Pilot centre now recovering
153126	P2↑	FL100			Worrupt profile
153249	P2↑	FL100			Recommence profile.
154329	P2↑	FL220			Worrupt profile
154529	P2↑	FL220			Recommence profile.
154500	P2↑	FL270			END.
155115		FL230			New2 TWC = 0.05 gm^{-3} New2 LWC @ J4 = 0 gm^{-3}
155733	R17	FL230			Cloud above us
155929	R17	FL230			END
160313	R18	FL250			START

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B252

Date:13/12/06 **Operator:** MAP **DRS Time:** 09:35:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 1 of 1**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:35:00																2D2-C very noisy switched off till runs	
12:24:30	2	0.17	94	1000	100	Off		Noise								Start Profile 1 from FL300	
12:25:41	2	0.14	98					Noise								FL290	
12:26:33	1	0.03						Noise								FL280	
12:27:30	2	0.12						Noise								FL270	
12:28:22	5	0.12	99	20	2			Noise								FL260	
12:29:15	4	0.08		1	1			Noise								FL250	
12:30:12	17	0.37	115	1000	3000			Noise								FL240	
12:31:09	4	0.37	166	1500	1500			Noise								FL230	
12:31:48	4	0.37	179	1500	1500											FL220	
12:32:45	5	0.13	186	10	1											FL210	
12:36:07	7	0.09	188	10	1											FL200	
12:37:20	3	0.07														FL190	
12:38:09	1	0.07														FL180	
12:39:21	15	0.08														FL170	
12:40:10	5	0.09														FL160	
12:41:15	5	0.09														End of Profile 1 @ FL150	
12:45:22																Start Run 1.1 @ FL200	
12:46:00	3	0.08	0					Noise								FFSSP restarted	
12:48:00	2	0.08						Noise									
12:50:19																End of Run 1.1	
12:52:24																Start Run 2.1 @ FL200	
12:53:00	4	0.08						Noise									
12:55:00	4	0.09						Noise									
12:57:00	3	0.07						Noise									
12:59:00	6	0.20	1	10	1			Noise									
13:01:00	3	0.10	2					Noise									
13:01:47																End of Run 2.1	
13:06:10																Start Run 3.1 @ FL200	
13:07:00	4	0.09		3	1			Noise									
13:09:00	3	0.12		15	5			Noise									
13:11:00	4	0.08						Noise									
13:13:00	3	0.07	3					Noise									
13:15:00	2	0.07						Noise									
13:17:00	3	0.09						Noise									
13:19:00	3	0.08						Noise									
13:21:00	3	0.06						Noise									
13:22:07																End of Run 3.1	
13:26:13																Start Run 4.1 @ FL230	
13:27:00	4	0.07	65	5	1			Noise									
13:29:00	3	0.08		3				Noise									
13:31:00	3	0.11	67	60	5			Noise									
13:33:00	1	0.09	68					Noise									
13:35:47																End of Run 4.1	
13:38:25																Start Run 5.1 @ FL250	
13:39:00	1	0.05		2	1			Noise									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B252

Date:13/12/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:41:00	1	0.05	106	2				Noise									
13:41:26																End of Run 5.1	
13:44:21																Start Run 5.2 @ FL245	
13:45:00	1	0.06		2				Noise									
13:45:47																End of Run 5.2	
13:49:10																Start Run 6.1 @ FL250	
13:50:00	2	0.07	121	5	1			Noise									
13:52:00	1	0.05						Noise									
13:52:15																End of Run 6.1	
13:56:17																Start Run 7.1 @ FL255	
13:57:00	1	0.03						Noise									
13:58:53																End of Run 7.1	
14:02:27																Start Run 8.1 @ FL250	
14:03:00	2	0.07						Noise									
14:05:00	1	0.05	167	2000	1000			Noise									
14:06:02																End of Run 8.1	
14:10:14																Start Run 9.1 @ FL245	
14:11:00	1	0.05	168	1000	2000			Noise									
14:13:12																End of Run 9.1	
14:15:48																Start Run 10.1 @ FL240	
14:16:00	1	0.08	212	1				Noise								54992 50658	
14:18:00	2	0.09	280	2000	2000			Noise									
14:19:21																End of Run 10.1	
14:22:57																Start Run 11.1 @ FL235	
14:23:00	1	0.06	284					Noise									
14:25:00	1	0.06	344					Noise									
14:25:42																End of Run 11.1	
14:29:13																Start Run 11.2 @ FL235	
14:30:00	1	0.06															
14:32:00	1	0.06	466	2000	1500												
14:32:16																End of Run 11.2	
14:36:50																Start Run 12.1 @ FL230	
14:37:00	1	0.11		2000	2000												
14:38:50																End of Run 12.1	
14:41:36																Start Run 13.1 @ FL225	
14:42:00	3	0.08	505	1													
14:44:00	2	0.07	555	2000	2000												
14:46:20			Reset													End of Profile 13.1	
14:54:28																Start Run 14.1 @ FL220	
14:55:00	2	0.61	21	3000	900												
14:56:20																End of Run 14.1	
14:58:23																Start Run 15.1 @ FL235	
14:59:00	1	0.07															
15:01:00	2	0.09	77	2000	3000												
15:02:16																End of Run 15.1	
15:07:20																Start Run 16.1 @ FL230	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B252

Date: 13/12/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
15:08:00	3	0.07	80	2000	2000												
15:09:50																End of Run 16.1	
15:26:00	15	0.08	201	10	1											Start Profile 2 from FL050	
15:27:25	10	0.08		1												FL060	
15:28:30	3	0.08		1	1											FL070	
15:29:35	15	0.08	202	1	1											FL080	
15:30:30	15	0.09		1	1											FL090	
15:31:26	25	0.08		1	1											FL100	
15:33:43	3	0.08		1	1											FL110	
15:34:35	15	0.07														FL120	
15:35:29	10	0.07														FL130	
15:36:17	15	0.07														FL140	
15:37:12	12	0.07		1	1											FL150	
15:38:05	13	0.08	203													FL160	
15:38:58	10	0.07		10	10											FL170	
15:40:00	5	0.07	Fail	3000	3000											FL180	
15:41:00	3	0.07														FL190	
15:43:30	1	0.07	Fail													FL220	
15:47:17	16	0.07	1	100	10			Noise								FL240	
15:48:16	20	0.19	3	1000	10			Noise								FL250	
15:49:00	5	0.34	5	1000	20			Noise								FL260	
15:50:05	12	0.30	9	1000	80			Noise								End of Profile 2 @ FL270	
15:57:35																Start Run 17 @ FL230	
15:58:00	1	0.07	26					Noise									
15:59:31																End of Run 17	
16:03:15																Start Run 18 @ FL250	
16:04:00	1	0.05		2				Noise									
16:06:00	1	0.3	27	100	1			Noise									
16:08:00	1	0.07	31	10	2			Noise									
16:09:03																End of Run 18	
16:13:27																Start Run 19.1 @ FL270	
16:14:00	17	0.54	41	400	20			Noise									
16:16:00	1	0.21	47	200	15			Noise									
16:17:28																End of Run 19.1	
16:18:49																Start Run 19.2 @ FL270	
16:19:00	2	0.28	56	100	5			Noise								54992 50656	
16:21:00	1	0.12	58	80	5			Noise									
16:22:13																End of Run 19.2	
	PCASP Flowrate = 1.1 CC/sec																
	2D2-C Off for flight as too noisy																
	2D2-P Noisy at high altitudes																
	FFSSP failed a few times due to excessive particle counts																
	CIP100 not working																

Flight:

B252

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Report Created 14/12/2006 18:43:15

Last Updated:

13/12/2006 17:57:30

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B252

Date: 13th December 2006

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS – u/s
2. TWC - u/s
3. Core Chemistry ethernet connection – problem with rack hub or cable so can't access HORACE displays. Ran a cable direct to Stbd Aft hub in flight then okay.
4. Turb Probe – Pitot port iced up at 1400. Attack and Sideslip Check iced up at start of descent (15:15Z) to clear icing from Turb Probe! Pitot port last to clear at 1532Z (took ~ 5 minutes at +2degC).
5. Downward Facing Camera picture on Aft Core Console very indistinct. Message “motion alarm area 1” appears occasionally. Can't make out clouds during most of the flight. Picture better on Video Recorder.

Aircraft

1. Flight Intercom very noisy pre-engine-start. Co-pilot's headset plug not seated properly, re-seat then okay.

Satcom H Calls - Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B252:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting completion of processing
Pre-flighter	No log created
Core Chemistry	pre flight operator only, unmanned in-flight operation (on auto calibrate) so no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2 Feb 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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Flight B252 12:21:35

Heading 292 deg Speed 342 knots Height 30.0kft Press 300mb

Lat 53°0.0'N Long 4°42.0'W Wind 36 ms-1/ 275 deg

Temp -44.64C Dewpoint -44.27C

From 10:50:26 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	300.54	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-44.64	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-44.28	deg C